

////////////////////////////////////

EMOTIONAL EFFECT OF FONTS DURING CHINESE READING PROCESS

Te-ping Tseng / Min-yuan Ma / Kuo-hsiang Chen
Department of Industrial Design, National Cheng Kung University
to_owllight@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

This research addressed how font selections affect reading emotions in Chinese reading. The paper assumed that: (1) font emotions could offer readers enough clues to arouse reader emotions when reading a narrative, which is emotion-absent itself; (2) reader emotions are enhanced or suppressed by font-article combinations. This interaction has also an effect on the speed with which an article segment is read. To examine the assumption, subjects were asked to read several article stimuli with different combination of fonts. By the use of eye-tracking, readers' eye movements were recorded. After Repeated Measure of ANOVA was adopted, the result shows that font emotions do reach significant level to affect reader emotions, whether font and article emotions may not interact. On the other hand, in physiological, readers' reading speeds were not affected by font selection. Styles of writing and difficulty might be the prime reason to affect readers' reading speeds.

Keywords: Reading, Font, Emotion

INTRODUCTION

Reading is an event that happens every day in our daily life. By reading, we acquire knowledge, get information, communicate with others and sometimes keep ourselves from dangers. On the other hand, it happens in Asian comic books that fonts were used to express different feeling of characters. We also could see sometimes graphic designers using fonts design in cope with different demand of message delivering. It is these styles of lettering convey different messages of their own, (Bartram, 1982; Brumberger, 2003; Rowe, 1982)

which was termed "typeface semantics."(Childers & Jass, 2002)

This research was aimed at the possibility that typeface semantics could be and aid on reading process, providing clues for reader and affecting the judgment about the contexts.

ARTICLE, FONT AND READER EMOTIONS

The characteristic of literature, compared to other types of discourse, is the emotional impact it can have on the reader (Brewer and Ohtsuka, 1988; Tan, 1994). Reader could feel what character feels inside the story, as they make meaningful sense of the work, readers can also respond emotionally to it, experiencing 'fresh' emotions in the moment (Larsen and Seilman, 1988) or emotional memories that resonate to thematic elements (Scheff, 1979). However, article is not the only thing that sending emotional messages to reader. Fonts could also make reader feel the emotions.

Chinese word system has been developed for thousands years. Under different style of calligraphy, fonts were hence created. These visual properties of typefaces are conceptualized as communicating unique semantic associations to individuals distinct from the content of the written words they clothe (Childers & Jass). In design stand, graphic designers know that to use fonts in sending different messages. They know the importance of the typeface semantics, and often judge them by experience, whether they never thoroughly understand them. In fact, few researches have discussed typeface semantics in Chinese. Feng (2007) constructed a system, adapted from the Latin font classification system, PANOSE SYSTEM 2.0 to archive Chinese font characteristics. The relations between the characteristics and the Kansei phrases were

analyzed. Later on, Tseng (2010) has also constructed an emotional map of Chinese fonts, which shows that the emotion of font can be traced by its congruity with reader's mental model, and its pressure derived from the historic degree. Both reading and the typeface affect readers' emotion. However, is it possible that font and article "interact" when reading? Will a sad story become sadder when using "sad" fonts? Or, will happy story become not so happy when applying "unhappy" fonts? To understand the relation between reading process and typeface semantics could be a new category of research and a guideline for designers on font selecting.

EXPERIMENT ARRANGEMENT

In order to understand the mechanism how font and article interact, the arrangement includes font selection, text analysis and context selection.

FONT SELECTION

Two experiment groups of font were chosen based on Tseng's (2010) research. The criterion is to choose the font that is the closest to the target emotions. This study also defined two emotions—positive and negative, with definitions below:

- Positive group: The group that contain higher joy and surprise emotions which may arouse reader's feeling in positive way.
- Negative group: The group that contain higher sadness and fear emotions which may depress reader's feeling to a lower state.

With two experiment group and one control group, figure 1 shows the final font samples chosen.

- (a) 情緒飛揚
(b) 情緒低落
(c) 心平氣和

Fig 1. Font sample selection. (a) positive; (b) negative; (c) control group.

TEXT ANALYSIS

Texts are selected into three groups—one as control group without obvious emotions, and the rests are positive and negative emotions, respectively, as

experiment groups—based on the emotions they conveyed. To determine and control the strength of emotions in each group, Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) was adopted to analyze the strength of emotion either positive or negative in the segments. LSA was proposed by Deerwester et al. (1990), which is mainly discussed the meaning underneath the texts. It is a theory and method for extracting and representing the contextual-usage meaning of words by statistical computations applied to a large corpus of text (Landauer et al., 1998). The underlying idea is that the aggregate of all the word contexts in which a given word does and does not appear provides a set of mutual constraints that largely determines the similarity of meaning of words and sets of words to each other.

This research applies Chinese Semantic Space built by Chen et al. The Space was based on Academic Sinica Corpus of Modern Chinese.

(<http://miniurl.com/110838>). It is also examined that the Chinese semantic space is a valid way to represent Chinese reader's world knowledge. (Chen et al., 2009)

CONTEXT SELECTION

The main idea is to sort out three emotion context groups, negative, neutral, and positive groups, corresponded to three emotion font groups in this step. Hence, the contexts were selected from two groups—the control group (for neutral emotion) and the experiment groups (for negative & positive emotions).

Control group

The segments were picked up from elementary level. 24 exposition segments were selected to be neutral in emotion. 3 segments were finally chosen in 3 different categories to prevent learning curve effect.

Experiment groups

Texts difficulty was controlled at junior high school level. Firstly, 95 excerpts were chosen subjectively with the emotions they conveyed. Then, those segments that are too short or too long were filtered. 28 positive (mean: 28.43 words; std. error: 3.77 words) and 24 negative excerpts (mean: 29.38 words; std. error: 6.95 words) were left in this section. Continually, the strength of emotion in

both positive (joy + surprise) and negative (sadness + fear) emotions were calculated by applying LSA. Finally, 3 positive and 3 negative emotion segments were selected into the next step.

EXPERIMENT

Subjects were asked to read segments. After each segment, their emotions and eye movements would be recorded. By applying statistical analysis the relations between font and article emotion could be both examined in physical and physiological dimensions.

METHOD

Subjects were asked to read 9 article segments selected from the former steps in random order. These segments contain 3 emotion levels (positive, control group, and negative), both in article and in fonts.

After each segment is read, 2 questions should be answered: the first is to obtain subjects feeling about each segment in 5-scale Likert scoring method; the second is a simple question of understanding to make sure that the subjects do read and understand the article. The process of the experiment would be informed to the subjects before they start the experiment in order to lower their uneasiness when answering a popping up question.

Subjects

29 graduate and undergraduate students (18 male, 11 female; avg. 24.4 years old) with university Chinese education level (avg. 6.45 years, std. deviation 2.44 years) participated during the experiment.

Materials & Apparatus

9 excerpts are the materials of the test. Subjects were asked to read once a segment on the screen in a row. The definition of the screen is 800*600; the size of the words is 18pt; the color of words is black, while the background is 15% grey, to make it comfortable to read; the cameras to capture eye movements and the infrared sensor was set under the screen. Subjects' jaw was fixed during the experiment.

Procedure

- **Calibration:** The eye-tracking system was firstly calibrated in accordance with subjects' characteristics, e.g., appearance, pose, etc.
- **Introduction:** The process of the experiment was introduced. Subjects could also practice during this phase.
- **Segments Reading:** Nine segments were read and the questions followed were asked to be answered.
- **Analyzing:** two types of data would be obtained—psychological measurement and physiological measurement. In physiological measurement, three kinds of data were to be examined: Total Fixation Duration (TFD), Average Fixation Duration (AFD), and Total Fixation Points (TFP).

DISCUSSION

The experiment data contains: psychological measurement and physiological measurement. The experiment was set as a within subjects experiment, with two factors (font and article), which may properly apply repeated measure ANOVA.

The results of psychological measurement showed that: (1) article emotion factors and font emotion factors are both reached significant level ($F=44.376$, $p < 0.05$ & $F=4.196$, $p = 0.027 < 0.05$, respectively); (2) the interaction between article and font emotional factors didn't reach significant level. In other words, articles with corresponding emotion fonts didn't enhance the readers' feelings of that emotion, and vice versa.

On the other hand, the results of physiological measurement showed that: (1) all kinds of test couldn't reach significant level with Total Fixation Duration; (2) the test of article factors reached significant level under Average Fixation Duration ($F=5.725$ · $p = 0.010 < 0.05$). What's more, the control article was obviously taking longer time to read than other two experiment groups and reached significant level. ($p = 0.14 < 0.05$ & $p = 0.005 < 0.05$); (3) the test of Total Fixation Points doesn't reach significant level under each factor.

RESULTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

The result implies that those who with Chinese education above university level could sense the difference between different font usage under same type of article. Meanwhile, as model assumed, fonts could be effective upon the emotion evaluation about articles to readers after reading, both in expository and lyrical texts.

However, positive emotion font does not significantly bring positive articles more “positive” in emotion recognition process and vice versa. The reason may lie on the strength difference between two stimuli. Compared to the strength of article, fonts make little contribution toward emotion recognition process.

Table 1 shows the mean difference of each group pair. The maximum mean difference is 5.376.

(I) article	(J) article	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error
negative	control	-3.494*	.373
	positive	-5.376*	.640
control	negative	3.494*	.373
	positive	-1.882*	.439
positive	negative	5.376*	.640
	control	1.882*	.439

* p<0.05

Table 1. Article type in psychological measurement

(I) font	(J) font	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error
negative	control	-.262	.179
	positive	-.565*	.219
control	negative	.262	.179
	positive	-.303	.282
positive	negative	.565*	.219
	control	.303	.282

* p<0.05

Table 2. Font type in psychological measurement

Meanwhile, Table 2 shows the mean difference, pair wisely. The maximum mean difference is 0.565. It is obvious that article provides greater effect than font did. The result may imply that article is itself stronger than font on emotion transmission. On the other hand, the inappropriateness of the sample selection in this experiment may also be the reason. In fact, there is no reference about how to control

the strength between font and emotion, which may be a way in further research.

RESULTS OF PHYSIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

In this part, three types of eye-tracking data were examined—Total Fixation Duration (TFD), Average Fixation Duration (AFD), and Total Fixation Points (TFP). Based on the result, test of article to AFD reached significant level, and what is more, both the experiment groups spend shorter time on cognition. The reason may lie on two facts: the difference between article types, or the difficulty of each article.

In the beginning of the experiment, the type of control group article (i.e. expository text) was different from the experiment groups (i.e. lyrical text) in order to control the emotions. The result shows that Average Fixation Duration of reading expository text was longer than reading lyrical text, which is consistent with the research of Ko. et al. (2005).

On the other hand, the difficulty of each article was controlled generally. All the text segments were selected from junior high school readings and below. However, the particular difference remain exist and was proven non-ignorable.

Segments No.	Mean (s)	Std. Deviation	N
1	9.973	4.027	26
2	6.662	2.582	26
3	9.617	4.196	26
4	6.875	2.987	26
5	10.678	5.615	26
6	8.051	3.639	26
7	10.253	5.159	26
8	8.121	4.020	26
9	5.719	2.446	26

Table 3. Segment descriptive statistics

Table 3 shows Total Fixation Duration of each segment. The main effect of segment difference reach significant level (F=10.709 , p<0.05). Figure 2 shows Segments to Total Fixation Duration. Numbers in the parenthesis represent the segments that each excerpt reached significant level with.

Figure 2. Segments to Total Fixation Duration

On The other hand, the difficulty of an article is properly related to the Information Mass (IM) of Chinese characters (Ma et al., 2006). The concept was adopted in this paper to examine the relation between Total Fixation Duration and segment difficulty.

The equation of IM is:

$$IM = IV \times ID, \text{ which}$$

IV: Information Volume (total numbers of characters);

ID: Information Density (strokes of character/appeared frequency);

The IM of each segment hence can be acquired, as shown in the table below (Table 5).

The relation between Information Mass and Total Fixation Duration has reached significant level ($p=0.046 < 0.05$). In other words, segments difficulty does affect reader’s Total Fixation Duration, with the correlations 0.676 (Table 4).

		IM	TFD
Information Mass (IM)	Pearson Correlation	1	.676*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.046
	N	9	9
Total Fixation Duration (TFD)	Pearson Correlation	.676*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.046	
	N	9	9

* $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed)

Table 4. Pearson correlation test

Segment No.	Content	IM
1	浣熊寄身在天然的岩縫或樹洞內，但一定選擇靠近有水的地方。 Raccoons choose habitat in rock joints or hollows and that close to water.	106.78
2	螢火蟲的閃光也是一種自然光。牠的光不會燙人，被叫做冷光。 Fireflies produce a "cold light" because it is not hot. It is also a natural light.	16.71
3	這時期的蕨類佔盡當時植物社會的優勢，因此有人又把石炭紀叫做「蕨類時代」。 Ferns dominated the plant society in this period. Hence people called Carboniferous Period "The period of ferns."	57.13
4	我喜歡那些像鐘一般準確出現的小販的叫賣聲。 I like the vender's shouting appeared as accurate as clocks.	4.43
5	隔著疏落的竹籬便看到牠們在陽光照耀的草地上，快活的跳動著、嬉戲著。 I can see them hopping and playing lively on the sunshine grass through the fence.	60.46
6	冰花瞬間溶化，溶入舌尖，那種沁涼暢快的感覺，足以將豔陽溶化掉。 Ice cream flakes just melt immediately into the tongue. That fresh feeling is going to melt the sun.	38.99
7	兔兒們平時是不會叫的，但那時，白兔同小兔的喉間卻發出了絲絲的微響。 Bunnies don't cry as usual. But then, rabbits made a sound slightly as silk.	16.14
8	那離別的時候，各自的辛酸與寂寞都不堪言說，便只是靜靜流下的無言的淚水罷。 Till the time of leaving, the bitter and loneliness of each other were unbearable to tell. The only thing they could do is tearing silently.	21.35
9	牠的眼睛顯出痛楚的神色，絕望地晃著腦袋。 She looked pain from her eyes, swaying her head in despairs.	5.792

Table 5. Segments and Information Mass (IM)

CONCLUSION

The study discussed how font selection could affect the judgments of feeling in reading. In sum, the research shows that: (1) font selection could affect readers’ judgments when reading, with corresponding emotion reaction. However, the

interaction between font and article doesn’t reach significant level. The possible reason may reflect that the intensity of article was far stronger than what fonts can provide. (2) Changing font usage couldn’t increase speed on reading cognition hence could bring no help on reading fluency. The reason may lie on the fact of article type—expository text,

the material of control group in this study—takes longer Average Fixation Duration than lyrical texts. Besides, the difficulty of segments could also make influence on reading comprehension hence should be well-controlled.

Reading is powerful. To understand the process of reading during different font use could reveal more about human reading process. It could be a guideline for designer to operate the emotion of a segment that how to be more sensitive and touching to reader's hearts. On the other hand, educator may apply it for helping children in learning stage to make reading even more interesting.

REFERENCES

- Bartram, D. (1982) The perception of semantic quality in type: Differences between designers and non-designers, *Information Design Journal*, Vol. 3, 38-50
- Brewer, W.F. and Ohtsuka, K. (1988) Story structure, characterization, just world organization, and reader affect in American and Hungarian short stories, *Poetics*, Vol. 17, 395-415.
- Brumberger, E. (2003) The rhetoric of typography: The persona of typeface and text, *Technical Communication*, Vol. 50, No.2, 206-223
- Chen, M.L., Wang, H.C., Ko, H.W. (2009) The Construction and Validation of Chinese Semantic Space by Using Latent Semantic Analysis, *Chinese Journal of Psychology*, Vol. 51, No. 4, 415-435
- Childers, T.L., & Jass, J.F. (2002) All dressed up with something to say: Effects of typeface semantic associations on brand perceptions and consumer memory, *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, Vol. 12, No.2, 93-106
- Deerwester S.C., Dumais, S.T., Landauer, T.k., George W. Furnas, G.W., Harshman, R.A. (1990) Indexing by Latent Semantic Analysis, *JASIS*, Vol. 41, No.6, 391-407
- Dijkstra, K., Zwaan, R.A., Graesser, A.C., Magliano, J.P. (1994) Character and Reader Emotions in Literary Texts, *Poetic*, Vol. 23, 139-157
- Feng, Y.C. (2007) The Characteristics and Styles of Chinese Typeface, NCKU M.D.,
- Huang, J.S., Ma, M.Y. (2007) A study on the cognitive of complexity and difficulty of chinese characters when reading and recognizing, *Displays*, Vol. 28, No.1, 8-25.
- Ko, H.W., Chen, M.L., Liao, C.N. (2005) Frequency Effect, Word Class and Eye Movements: Evidence from Text Reading, *Chinese Journal of Psychology*, Vol. 47, No. 4, 381-398
- Landauer, T. K., Foltz, P. W., & Laham, D. (1998) Introduction to Latent Semantic Analysis, *Discourse Processes*, Vol. 25, 259-284
- Larsen, S.F. and Seilman, U. (1988) Personal reminders while reading literature, *Text* 8, 411-429.
- Rowe, C.L. (1982) The connotative dimensions of selected display typefaces, *Information Design Journal*, Vol. 3, No.1, 30-37
- Scheff, T.J. (1979) *Catharsis in healing, ritual, and drama*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Tseng, T.P., Ma, M.Y. (2010) Emotions & Fonts: Constructing Emotional Map of Chinese Fonts, *International Conference of Kansei Engineering and Emotion Research*, March 2-4, Paris, France, 53